

DESIGN OF GRAY-SCALE NONLINEAR FILTERS VIA MULTIREOLUTION APERTURES

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ABSTRACT

This paper applies pyramidal multiresolution design, which has been used to design binary filters, to design aperture filters, which are nonlinear gray-scale filters that operate on data in a range-domain window (aperture). The designed filters are used to find markers for the region of the eyes in an image database of faces.

1 INTRODUCTION

Pyramidal multiresolution design [1] is a powerful and effective method to design filters. The method is being applied to design binary filters [1], and now to design aperture filters [2], which are nonlinear gray-scale filters that operate on data in a range-domain window (aperture). The purpose of multiresolution is to be able to use larger apertures, and therefore improve filter performance, while at the same time not succumbing to unacceptable design error on account of the large aperture.

The key problem in designing optimal windowed filters is that the data requirement for good filter estimation grows exponentially in response to increasing window size, thereby making satisfactory design problematic for large windows. Various approaches have been taken to mitigate the data requirement using prior knowledge, these being generally categorized into (1) constraint of the filter class over which optimization is to be achieved [3, 4] and (2) use of the probability characteristics of the problem for filter design. A method proposed recently to constrain the filter consists of multiresolution observation of images to create equivalence classes of operators.

The data problem for aperture filters is analogous to binary windowed filters, except that it is intensified. As in the case of binary filters, multiresolution can be employed for design to mitigate the data requirement. This paper applies multiresolution design to aperture filters and demonstrates the benefit of multiresolution design, namely, the ability to use a larger aperture (and therefore see more of the signal) in defining the filter.

Following this introduction, Section 2 reviews the important concepts of aperture filters and their statistical

design. Section 3 reviews the multiresolution design for binary operators and introduces the method for aperture operators; Section 4 presents the methodology used in some experiments of multiresolution design of aperture filters for segmentation. Finally, Section 5 presents some conclusions and directions for future work.

The results obtained in the experiments cannot be shown here appropriately but they are available at our web site: <http://www.vision.ime.usp.br/demos>.

2 APERTURE FILTERS FOR SEGMENTATION

An aperture is a product between a window W in the domain of a signal and a window K in the range. If $X_1, X_2, \dots, X_n$ are the gray-scale random variables defined over W and the observations are constrained to $K = -k, -k + 1, \dots, k$, then, for $j = 1, 2, \dots, n$, we define the truncated random variable

$$X_j^* = \begin{cases} X_j & : -k \leq X_j \leq k \\ k & : X_j > k \\ -k & : X_j < -k \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

and let $X^* = (X_1^*, X_2^*, \dots, X_n^*)$. Filters of the form $\Psi(X^*)$ are called aperture filters, the aperture being the product set $W \times K$. Observations within $W \times K$ are unchanged prior to application of Ψ and those outside of $W \times K$ are projected vertically into the boundary of $W \times K$ (from above or below).

Relative to Y (the random variable to be estimated), the optimal constrained filter for binary classification ($\Psi(X^*) \in \{0, 1\}$) is the one that minimizes the classification error, which is equivalent to minimizing the *Mean Absolute Error*, MAE, of Ψ ($MAE\langle\Psi\rangle = E[|\Psi(X^*) - Y|]$).

Definition 2.1 Let $P(x^*) = P(X^* = x^*)$ be the probability of observing x^* , a realization of X^* . Let $p(1|x^*) = P(Y = 1|x^*)$ be the conditional probability of observing value 1 given the observation x^* . The MAE optimal operator is given by:

$$\psi_{opt}(x^*) = \begin{cases} 1, & \text{if } p(1|x^*) > 0.5, \\ 0, & \text{if } p(1|x^*) \leq 0.5. \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

This paper concerns aperture operators for binary classification but the general definition of aperture filters for classification allows larger (non-binary) output ranges.

A W -operator ψ_W locally defines a signal operator Ψ_W by:

$$\Psi_W(f)(t) = \begin{matrix} \psi_W(f(W_t)) = \\ \psi_W(f(t+w_1), \dots, f(t+w_n)) \end{matrix} \quad (3)$$

By appropriately indexing $w_1, w_2, \dots, w_n$, the window can be centered at t or be located in some other manner. For an aperture signal operator Ψ_A defined via an aperture function ψ_A , the window $W \times K$ must be placed into the product space of the domain and the range. A range point z must be chosen so that the signal is observed through the window $W_t \times K_z$. Relative to the signal operator,

$$\Psi_A(f)(t) = \psi_A(f_{-z}(W_t)) \quad (4)$$

where f_{-z} is the range translation of f by z .

Besides the estimation of the local operator ψ_A from sample signal data, the design involves the representation of ψ_A in some computational form. ψ_A is estimated from training pairs of the form $\mathbf{x}^* = (x^*, y)$ extracted from pairs of signal realizations [5]. We call $\mathbf{x}^*$ a *training example*, y its *label* and denote the set of labeled examples by $\mathcal{M}_A$. It is important to notice that $\mathcal{M}_A$ defines partially the operator ψ_A . Let $\psi_{A,N}$ represent all operators whose kernel are consistent with $\mathcal{M}_A$, i.e., $\psi_{A,N}(x^*) = y$ for all $\mathbf{x}^* \in \mathcal{M}_A$, where $N = |\mathcal{M}_A|$. Of course, if $\mathcal{M}_A$ contains all possible realizations of X^* then, $\psi_{A,N} = \psi_A$ [6], otherwise there are more than one operator that shares the same $\mathcal{M}_A$.

It is critical that the computational representation extends the definition of $\psi_{A,N}$ from $\mathcal{M}_A$ in a consistent manner, meaning that if y is the final label for $\mathbf{x}^* \in \mathcal{M}_A$, then, upon representation, the operator must assign y to x^* . Given this consistency, the definition of $\psi_{A,N}$ is unambiguous. In machine learning, this extension is called *prediction*, or *generalization*, because the extension “predicts”, or “generalizes” a learned concept. Prediction is important because the performance of a designed operator depends on it. We use decision trees [7, 8, 9] to represent the operator.

3 MULTIREOLUTION DESIGN

In this section we recall some concept of binary multiresolution design and present the way to extend the method for aperture filters.

Let D_0 be the class of all possible vectors in an n -pixel window W_0 . If the domain of the filter is binary, the cardinality of D_0 is 2^n . Let D_1 be the class of all possible vectors in an n_1 -pixel window $W_1 \subset W_0$. Let $\xi_1 : D_0 \rightarrow D_1$ be a mapping between D_0 and D_1 . We call ξ_1 a *resolution constraint mapping*. For any observation $x \in D_0$, $\xi_1(x) \in D_1$, and conversely, for any $z \in D_1$, there exists a subset of D_0 such that $z = \xi_1(x)$.

The most straightforward multiresolution involves a coarser window W_1 such that, for every $x \in D_0$, $\xi_1(x)$ is a binary vector over W_1 . If $z \in D_1$ and $N(z)$ is the number of times z is observed in training, then

$$N(z) = \sum_{x:\xi_1(x)=z} N(x) \quad (5)$$

Thus, the data requirement for estimating probabilities necessary for filter design is decreased at the lower resolution. This idea can be repeated until the size of W_i (the window i -th constrained) is 1. Figure 1 shows an example where ξ_1 maps each four pixels from window W_0 to one pixel in W_1 and ξ_2 maps each two pixels from window W_1 to one pixel in W_2 .

For binary filters, if the random variable Y is to be estimated by the optimal filter Ψ_{opt} , then $\Psi_{opt}(x) = 1$ if $P(Y = 1|x) > 0.5$ and $\Psi_{opt}(x) = 0$ if $P(Y = 1|x) \leq 0.5$. Standard training involves estimating $P(Y = 1|x)$ and defining the designed filter, $\Psi_{des}(x)$, via this estimation. Pyramidal multiresolution design involves defining $\Psi_{des}(x)$ according to the estimate of $P(Y = 1|x)$ if x is observed in training a sufficient number of times, and to define it at the lower resolution by $P(Y = 1|\xi_1(x))$ otherwise. Notice that the pyramidal multiresolution design is a form of generalization in the sense of learning theory [8].

Although the optimal filter at the higher resolution is better, the designed filter using multiresolution can outperform the standard designed filter owing to better probability estimates. The method is applied iteratively by a sequence of resolution-constraint operators $\xi_1, \xi_2, \dots, \xi_m$.

Figure 1: Pyramidal structure

The method of multiresolution can also be applied to the design of aperture filters, however choosing the resolution constraint mappings must also concern with the range. D_i is still the class of all possible vectors in an n_i -pixel window W_i but now the domain of the filter is graylevel. If $L_i \subset \mathbb{Z}$ is the range for resolution

i , there are $|L_i|^n$ possible vectors in D_i . The resolution constraint has to obey the pyramidal paradigm, i.e., the relation between the pairs (W_i, L_i) and (W_j, L_j) for $i > j$ has to be such that: $W_i \subset W_j$ and $L_i \subset L_j$. We have three possibilities: (i) constrain the window first, (ii) constrain the grayscale first and (iii) constrain both at the same time. Ultimately the constraint happens on both domain and range, but the question is: how is the best way to constrain the filter for estimation purposes? Or, in other words, what is the best pyramid to represent the knowledge about the filter class considered?

4 APPLICATION METHODOLOGY

To test the efficacy of the multiresolution approach for aperture filters, we present an experiment for finding the region of the eyes in a database of faces. For higher window resolutions, these regions can be used as markers to segment the eyes using Beucher-Meyer paradigm [10, 11]. The database is composed by 300 different images of 30 persons. There are 10 pictures of each person’s face in different angles (looking front, left, right, up and down). The background and the lighting are controlled. There are 16 persons wearing glasses.

To train the operator we have chosen 20 images (5 from each angle) and trained different operators with 2, 4, 8, 12, 16 and 20 images. It is few compared with the amount of data in the database but one of the objectives is to test if multiresolution can help to solve the problem with fewer images. Figure 2a shows an example of one of the images in the database. All images have 512×342 pixels in 8-bit grayscale. Figure 2b shows the expected result of the operator (ideal image).

The pyramidal design is described in Section 3. We have used in this application a particular generalization rule: the zeros attributed to low resolution observations are propagated to the corresponding higher resolution equivalent objects. That is, just the ones attributed in low resolutions may be changed by observations in higher resolutions. In practice, this can be implemented as a domain constraint defined by the low resolution image observations. Denoting by ξ_1 and ξ_2 the resolution constraint mappings, Fig. 3a and b show the observed and the respective ideal images for the observations constrained by ξ_2 ; Fig. 4a and b show the observed (with the zeros propagated from ξ_2) and the respective ideal images for the observations constrained by ξ_1 ; and Fig. 5a and b show the observed (with the zeros propagated from ξ_1) and respective ideal images for the unconstrained observations.

Figure 6 shows the dynamic of the zeros propagation. Each block represents all the possible vectors for a certain resolution constraint. The marked parts correspond to the zeros of the operator. The applied rule propagates the zeros from the lower resolution to the higher resolutions.

Figure 2: Observed and ideal images

Figure 3: Observed and ideal images - quarter

5 CONCLUSION

Multiresolution is important to solve complex problems in image operators design. It is being used successfully for binary and now it is being studied for gray-scale through aperture operators. The spatial combined with the range multiresolution can help the design but it is not well studied how to design this pyramid. These are some of the directions for future research on this subject.

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Figure 4: Observed and ideal images - half

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Figure 5: Observed and ideal images - full resolution

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Figure 6: Dynamic of the zeros propagation